

ALGORITHMS AND SOFTWARE FOR EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF VIRAL HEPATITIS BASED ON BLOOD IMAGING

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Abstract. *Hepatic fibrosis is a common middle stage of the pathological processes of chronic liver diseases. Clinical intervention during the early stages of hepatic fibrosis can slow the development of liver cirrhosis and reduce the risk of developing liver cancer. Performing a liver biopsy, the gold standard for viral liver disease management, has drawbacks such as invasiveness and a relatively high sampling error rate. Real-time tissue elastography (RTE), one of the most recently developed technologies, might be promising imaging technology because it is both noninvasive and provides accurate assessments of hepatic fibrosis. However, determining the stage of liver fibrosis from RTE images in a clinic is a challenging task. In this study, in contrast to the previous liver fibrosis index (LFI) method, which predicts the stage of diagnosis using RTE images and multiple regression analysis, we employed four classical classifiers to build a decision-support system to improve the hepatitis B stage diagnosis performance. The reliable diagnosis rate of diagnostic tests is provided by their intervals with acceptable accuracy (e.g. $\geq 90\%$) where a liver biopsy can be avoided. Aims: To evaluate the overall accuracy and improve the reliable diagnosis rates of blood tests for significant liver fibrosis. Thus, the main aim of this study was to describe comprehensively the performance of original blood tests in identifying intervals of reliable diagnosis, and to examine whether it was possible to improve reliable diagnosis rates for significant fibrosis. The secondary aims were to compare the overall accuracy and reliable diagnosis rates between several blood tests and evaluate other diagnostic targets.*

Keywords: *chronic liver diseases, artificial intelligence, fibrometer, microscopic blood image.*

Introduction

Hepatic fibrosis is a frequent intermediate phase in the pathological progression of chronic liver conditions. Clinical intervention in the early phases of hepatic fibrosis can decelerate the progression to liver cirrhosis and lower the risk of liver cancer development [1]. Performing a liver biopsy, the current gold standard for managing viral liver diseases, has limitations such as being invasive and having a relatively high rate of sampling errors. Real-time tissue elastography (RTE), one of the latest advancements in technology, presents a promising imaging technique as it is noninvasive and provides precise evaluations of hepatic fibrosis. However, determining the stage of liver fibrosis from RTE images in a clinical setting is a difficult task. In this study, as opposed to the previous liver fibrosis index (LFI) approach, which uses RTE images and multiple regression analysis to predict diagnostic stages, we applied four classical classifiers to develop a decision-support system aimed at enhancing the performance of hepatitis B stage diagnosis [2]. The dependable diagnosis rate of diagnostic tests is represented by their intervals with acceptable precision (e.g., $\geq 90\%$), where a liver biopsy can be avoided. Objectives: To assess the overall accuracy and enhance the reliable diagnosis rates of blood tests for significant liver fibrosis. Therefore, the primary objective of this study was to thoroughly describe the performance of original blood tests in identifying intervals of reliable diagnosis and to explore the possibility of improving reliable diagnosis rates for significant fibrosis. The

secondary objectives were to compare the overall accuracy and reliable diagnosis rates among various blood tests and evaluate other diagnostic outcomes.

METHODS

Data Source

Using the Medline database and a manual search, we systematically reviewed the literature from 2000 to 2017 for studies comparing FibroMeter and Fibrotest in patients with chronic viral hepatitis C for whom liver biopsy data were available. Information provided by the tests enabled Hepascore, APRI and Fib-4 to be calculated. Three independent publications were retrieved. The first study, involving one centre, Angers, was the original publication that described the FibroMeter test. The second study included two independent centres, Provence/Côte d'Azur (PACA) and Tours, and the third was from Grenoble. The PACA centre incorporated three secondary and two tertiary care settings. Angers and Bordeaux provided two additional, currently unpublished populations. Thus, individual patient data were available from five centres, independent for study design, patient recruitment, blood marker determination and interpretation of liver histology.

Patients

The inclusion and exclusion criteria were largely consistent across all five centers. Patients with chronic hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection were prospectively enrolled between 2000 and 2017 if they tested positive for anti-HCV antibodies, had detectable HCV RNA in the bloodstream, and had available liver biopsy results and blood markers. Fasting blood samples were obtained either immediately before or no later than 3 months after the liver biopsy. In the Tours and PACA centers, patients were excluded if their liver samples were smaller than 15 mm. Other exclusion criteria included additional causes of liver disease, especially co-infection with HIV or hepatitis B virus, complicated cirrhosis, anti-fibrotic treatment within the last 6 months, and alcohol consumption exceeding 30 g/day in the 5 years prior to inclusion. In total, the five centers contributed 1,535 patients; 479 were excluded due to missing criteria or data, resulting in a core group of 1,056 patients. The study protocol adhered to the ethical standards of the current Declaration and received approval from local ethics committees.

Blood Measurements

Blood samples were processed independently at each center. The variables assessed included platelet count, urea, bilirubin, γ -glutamyl transferase, aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase, prothrombin index, apolipoprotein A1, haptoglobin, hyaluronic acid (Corgenix), and α -2-macroglobulin (Dade Behring). Direct markers were measured either in fresh blood or in frozen serum samples stored at $\leq -20^{\circ}\text{C}$. Indirect markers were generally analyzed in fresh blood. Automated systems and assay techniques varied between centers (details not provided), except for apolipoprotein, α -2-macroglobulin, and hyaluronic acid. Blood test scores were calculated based on established formulas. The FibroMeter score was slightly enhanced by considering the patient's sex, as outlined in a previous study. AST used in the APRI was normalized by dividing by a common upper limit of normal, as several studies conducted in multiple laboratories demonstrated excellent reproducibility across labs.

Liver Biopsy

Liver biopsies were conducted using Menghini's technique with a needle diameter of 1.4–1.6 mm. The biopsy samples were preserved in a formalin–alcohol–acetic acid solution and embedded in paraffin; 5- μm -thick sections were then prepared and stained with haematoxylin–eosin–safran. Liver fibrosis was classified from F0 to F4 based on the Metavir scoring system.

Three diagnostic categories were defined as follows: significant fibrosis (primary target), F2+F3+F4; advanced fibrosis, F3+F4; and cirrhosis, F4. The readings were carried out by independent, blinded senior pathologists specializing in hepatology [2]. Histological evaluations were conducted twice by the same pathologist in Grenoble, once in Bordeaux, and once by each of two pathologists in Angers and Tours, with a joint final review in cases of disagreement. The biopsy samples were not centrally re-examined, as we demonstrated in a previous study (involving most of the same pathologists) that inter-observer agreement on the Metavir staging system is excellent among senior hepato-pathologists.

METHODOLOGY

End Points

The primary goal of this study was to assess the overall accuracy and reliable diagnosis rates of blood tests for significant fibrosis, as well as explore methods to improve the rate of reliable diagnoses [3]. The secondary goals were to assess the overall accuracy for other diagnostic targets, compare the effectiveness of different blood tests, and examine the consistency of predictive values.

Classification/Misclassification Rate

This approach was referred to as the ‘performance profile’ in a recent study. In summary, the misclassification rate of a blood test for significant fibrosis was calculated using the Metavir staging system as the benchmark. A patient with Metavir F0 or F1 who was categorized into the significant fibrosis group by the blood test was deemed misclassified, and the same applied in reverse. The misclassification rate was determined for each Metavir fibrosis (F) stage or for combinations of stages as established by histological staging. Finally, misclassification rates between pairs of blood tests were compared using the McNemar test. For simplicity, the results are primarily presented as the inverse of the proportion of correctly classified patients [5,6].

Statistical Analysis

The diagnostic accuracy of each test was expressed as the area under the receiver operating characteristic (AUROC), the overall accuracy and detailed indices such as likelihood ratio and diagnostic odds ratio. AUROCs were compared using the non-parametric DeLong test. Data were reported according to STARD statements and thus analysed on an intention-to-diagnose basis. Importantly, there was no exclusion owing to false blood test results [4]. The size of the population was that necessary to detect a significant difference between the two most accurate tests according to a preliminary study in the diagnosis of cirrhosis, which was the diagnostic target with the least difference between blood tests. With an α - risk of 0.05, a β - risk of 0.2, cirrhosis prevalence of 0.11, AUROC correlation of 0.75 and bilateral testing, the required sample size was 910 patients for the following AUROC values: FibroMeter: 0.93, Fibrotest: 0.89, as provided by the previous study.

According to weight sharing of CNN, the weight of feature images in pooling layer was often assigned with constant value α . The error signal σ_g^i of each feature image g in convolution layer could be generated by repeating the previous process.

$$\sigma_g^i = \sigma_g^{i+1} (f'(\sigma_g^i)) = up(\sigma_g^{i+1}) (1)$$

In equation (1), upsampling operation was illustrated. Based on the above analysis, the error signals through layer i could probably obtain the basic gradient of deviation, which was demonstrated in equation (2) as follows.

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial d_g} = \sum_{n,r} (\sigma_g^i)_{nr} (2)$$

In equation (3), p_i^{i-1} represented the patch generated by the multiplication of the convolution and the successive element R'_{ij} in Y_i^{i-1} .

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial K_{ig}^g} = \sum_{n,r} (\sigma_g^i)_{nr} (p_i^{i-1})_{nr} \quad (3)$$

The multiplication results of each element at (n,r) in the previous layer and corresponding convolution kernel determined the value of the position (n,r) in output convolution feature images [1].

Evaluation of Segmentation Effects of AI Segmentation Algorithm-Based CT Images

Liver segmentation plays a crucial role in digital simulation systems for liver and liver cancer surgery planning, as well as in supporting liver disease treatment. New technologies provide a visualized platform for liver cancer embolization, surgical incision planning, and interventional radiotherapy. Physicians can develop surgical strategies and design appropriate surgical plans based on the simulation system. Moreover, the number of surgeries can be minimized by selecting optimal surgical approaches, thus reducing injury. Improving the accuracy of tumor localization, surgical complexity, and the success rate of surgeries is essential. The key technical metrics are as follows: The first metric is autonomous segmentation accuracy, which should exceed 80%. In multiple dimensions, the liver's reconstruction accuracy can be observed from various angles, and the reconstruction precision should not be lower than the resolution of the original CT scan. The second metric is calculation error, which should be less than 8%. The volumes of the entire liver, liver segments, incised frontal liver, and remaining liver should all have an error margin below 8%. The simulation accuracy of virtual liver surgeries should match or exceed the resolution of the original CT input. Figure 2 displays a CT scan of the liver alongside segmentation results of target areas in the CT images produced by the algorithm used.

Fig. 1. Image of the liver.

Fig. 2. Diagnosing the disease in the image of the liver.

RESULTS

Patient Characteristics

The principal characteristics of the 1056 patients were as follows: sex: 59.5% male; mean age: 45.6 ± 12.5 years; Metavir F stage: F0: 4.4%, F1: 43.5%, F2: 27.0%, F3: 14.0%, F4: 11.2%; and mean liver specimen length: 21 ± 8 mm. Thus, the prevalence of the main diagnostic target, significant fibrosis, was 52%. There was no correlation between Metavir F stage and liver

specimen length (rs: 0.00, P=0.872), thus reflecting the pathologist expertise ; 90.0% of liver specimens were ≥ 15 mm and 58.2% were ≥ 20 mm.

REFERENCES

1. L. Wu, B. Ning, J. Yang, Y. Chen, C. Zhang., “Diagnosis of liver cirrhosis and liver fibrosis by artificial intelligence algorithm-based multislice spiral computed tomography,” *Meth. in Med.*, 2022.
2. F. Oberti, E. Valsesia, C. Pilette, et al., “Noninvasive diagnosis of hepatic fibrosis or cirrhosis,” *Gastro.*, vol. 113, pp. 1609–1616, 1997.
3. G. Sebastiani, A. Alberti, “Non invasive fibrosis biomarkers reduce but not substitute the need for liver biopsy,” *World J. Gastro. Vol. 12*, pp. 3682–3694, 2006.
4. F. Imbert-Bismut, V. Ratziu, L. Pieroni, F. Charlotte, Y. Benhamou, T. Poinard, “Biochemical markers of liver fibrosis in patients with hepatitis C virus infection: a prospective study,” *Lancet*, vol. 357, 1069–1075, 2001.
5. V. Leroy, M.N. Hilleret, N. Sturm, et al., “Prospective comparison of six non-invasive scores for the diagnosis of liver fibrosis in chronic hepatitis C,” *J. Hepat. vol. 46*, pp. 775–782, 2007.
6. Turgunov, “Application of mathematical modeling methods and use of information technologies for research of viral hepatitis B” *Inter.Conf. on Infor. Sci. and Comm. Tech.: App., Tren. and Oppor., ICISCT 2022*, vol. 9(7), pp. 1–4. 2020.
7. M. Hidirova, A. Turgunov, “A Method for Modeling the Regulation of the Introduction of Genetic Information of the Hepatitis B Virus into the Hepatocyte Genome” *Inter. Conf. of Youn. Special. on Mic./Nanotech. and Elec. Dev., EDM - 2024*, pp. 2480–2484, 2024.